

AN IMPERATIVE STUDY OF EFFICIENT IMAGE PROCESSING ALGORITHMS FOR LUNG CANCER DETECTION, SEGMENTATION AND CLASSIFICATION: A REVIEW

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Abstract.

The Lung cancer is one of the leading health issues contributing to the high mortality rate in the universe. The survival rate of lung cancer is very low compared to other cancers. At early stage only 15% of the patients with lung cancers were caught over decades and when it spreads to other organs the survival rate drops to 3.5%. Early detection of the disease is needed to reduce the mortality rate and help to increase the chances of survival rate. Over the last few years, the survival rate has increased from 15% to 49% due to the diagnosis of the disease at an initial stage. A computed Tomography (CT) image is effective to identify the presence of lung cancer. CT images with various image processing algorithms helps in early diagnosis of this disease. A good amount of research work has been carried out towards CAD system for the detection of lung cancer using CT images. It is divided into four stages: preprocessing nodule detection, nodule segmentation and classification. This paper presents in detail the imperative survey on various techniques that have been used in Pre-processing, nodule segmentation, detection and classification.

Keywords: CT images, CAD system, Cancer Detection, Image processing, Feature extraction, etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

The windpipe, the major airway, or in the lungs, Lung cancer can develop [1]. It is caused by the spread of specific cells in the lungs as well as unregulated cell proliferation. People who have a history of chest illness or emphysema are more prone to develop lung cancer [1].

The two most common types of lung cancer are small-cell lung carcinoma (SCLC) and non-small-cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC). SCLC is almost always associated with smoking and is increasing at a quicker rate. Non-small cell lung cancer is more frequent and spreads more slowly. It is known as combined small cell/large cell cancer [2].

According to current figures, around 234,030 new lung cancer cases were predicted to be diagnosed in 2018, with approximately 85 percent of these cases being non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) [3]. The development of lung cancer without symptoms is the most crucial aspect in making this illness so lethal. Almost a fifth of the population showed no symptoms of malignancy. Many individuals are aware that lung cancer has a secondary

disease that results in lung X-rays. Because lung cancer spreads swiftly, early detection is important. Imaging technology advancements such as low-dose computed tomography can now detect lung cancer in its early stages [4]. Lung cancer is caused by a tumour termed a nodule that develops from cells in the respiratory system's airways. In chest X-rays, these cells are always in direct contrast and take the shape of a spherical object. If lung nodules can be consistently diagnosed at an early stage, patient survival can be significantly increased. However, because lung nodules utilising raw chest X-ray imaging cannot be difficult process [5]. A tiny nodule discovered by a big 3D lung CT scan would have to be detected by the computer-aided diagnostic (CAD) system [6]. Figure 1 is a 2D slice of a CT scan showing an early-stage lung cancer nodule. The CT scan is filled with noise from the tissues around it, air, and bone, therefore this noise would have to be removed first. Figure 1: A 2D CT scan slice containing a tiny (5mm) nodule of early-stage lung cancer

[7] must be pre-processed in order for CAD systems to search successfully. Our classification pipeline includes image pre-processing, malignancy classification detection, and nodule candidate [8]. Machine learning techniques aid in the early diagnosis and assessment of lung nodules by evaluating CT images generated by artificial intelligence systems [9], [10].

Figure 1: 2D CT scan slice containing a small (5mm) early-stage Lung Cancer nodule [10].

Table1: Literature Review

Sl.no	Authors	Year	Database	Paper Approached for the Problem and Methods	Result
1.	Jianxin Feng and Jun Jiang	2022	CT and MRI images Collected data from various hospitals	Deep learning-based CT examination combined with serum tumor detection, factoring into Neurospecificenolase	accuracy of DPN algorithm model 88.74%, the accuracy of CT diagnosis of lung cancer was 88.37%, the sensitivity was 82.91%, and the specificity was 87.43%.
2.	Meraj Begum Shaikh Ismail	2021.	Dicom images from LIDC-IDRI, Kargal	For medical image processing many different types of images are used but Computer Tomography (CT) scans are generally preferred because of less noise.	precision with the classifiers is substantially higher at 41% compared to 1-2% by radiologists.
3.	Horry , M. Chakraborty	2021	LIDC - IDRI	new hybrid deep learning and decision tree-based computer vision	best decision tree attained sensitivity of 86.7% and specificity of 80.0%
4.	Xinrong Lu, Y.A Nanehkaran et.al,	2021	The RIDER dataset	Image processing, deep learning, and metaheuristic, an optimal method for untimely detection of lung cancer. Convolutional neural network is designed. Marine predators' algorithm deep networks such as CNN ResNet-18, Google Net, Alex Net, and VGG-19.	MPA-based method gave 93.45% accuracy, 98.42% sensitivity, and 97.1% specificity provides the highest efficiency with the least error (1.6)

5.	Heng Yu, et.al,	2020	Diagnostic Image Analysis Group	The Adaptive Hierarchical Heuristic Mathematical Model (AHHMM) has been projected for the deep learning approach.	96.67 % accuracy is obtained.
6.	Kubra Tuncal.et.al	2020	2012 World Health Organization and Globacan	Several machine learning algorithms have been proposed to provide effective and rapid prediction of uncertain raw data with minimized error.	Results show that Support Vector Regression performed superior results than other considered algorithms.
7.	Murat Aykanat,et.al	2020	Collected data from various hospitals	support vector machines (SVM), k-nearest neighbor (k-NN), and Gaussian Bayes (GB) algorithms	Accuracy results in SVM were %75, %88, %64, %73, %63, %70; for k-NN %95, %92, %92, %67, %64, %66; for GB %98, %91, %97, %58, %48, %58 respectively. SVM and k-NN are best in classifying

					the dataset in more than two classes. However GB is best when it comes to classifying into two classes.
8.	R. Madana Mohana	2019	LIDC	GLCM and Nearest Neighbour classifier	Accuracy obtained is 98.76%
9.	Singh and Gupta	2019	LIDC	Multinomial naive Bayes classifier, SVM classifier, k- nearest neighbors' classifier, stochastic gradient descent classifier, multi-layer perceptron (MLP) classifier and random forest classifier.	The accuracy of 88.555% is obtained by MLP
10.	Bhatia et al.,	2019	LIDC - IDRI	UNet and ResNet models are used to extract features. The extracted feature is given to classifiers such as i.e., XGBoost and Random Forest	Accuracy obtained 84%
11.	K.Mohanambal,et.al	2019	LIDC - IDRI	SCM successfully extracted features, Support vector machine is been used as a classifier	Results showed that SCM successfully extracted features
12.	Justin Monsi,et.al	2019	NIH chest X-ray dataset	Deep convolutional neuralnetwork	Accuracy of 90%

13.	Alam et al.,	2018	UCI machine learning database	Threshold and marker-controlled watershed-based segmentation and SVM multi classifier	The system gave a result of 97% for cancer identification and 87% to forecast the cancer
14.	Makaju et al.,	2018	LIDC	Watershed segmentation algorithm and SVM classifier	Accuracy obtained is 92%
15.	Xiang-Xia Li, Bin Li et.al	2018	Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC)	grey-level co-occurrence matrix, rotation invariant uniform local binary pattern and Gabor filter, RF classifier	sensitivity of 0.92 accuracy of 90%
16.	Alakwaa et al.,	2017	CT images from Kaggles DSB	3D convolutional neural network to spot nodules in cancer patients and predict important points using the U-Net architecture	accuracy of 86.6 %
17.	Qing Zeng, LeiZhaoet.al,	2017	Lung Image Database Consortium – Image Database Resource Initiative (LIDC-IDRI)	Deep Neural Networks	accuracy of 84.15%, sensitivity of 83.96% and specificity of 84.32%
18.	Hongyang Jiang, He Ma, Wei Qian et.al,	2017	Lung Image Database Consortium – Image Database Resource Initiative (LIDC-	Singular value decomposition (SVD), Convolutional neural network	Specificity- 88.5%, sensitivity 86% and AUC 91.3%

			IDRI)		
19.	Purvi Joshi, Saurbhi Chalki	2017	Vision & Image Analysis Group (VIA)	Gabor filter, Watershed Algorithm and masking	Accuracy of 95.1%
20.	Pol Cirujeda, Yashin Dicente et.al,	2016	SABR – Standard Cancer Institution	3-D Riesz-wavelets, SVM	Accuracy 82.7%
21.	Arnaud Arindra Diyoso Setio, Francesco Ciaompiet.al	2016	Lung Image Database Consortium – Image Database Resource Initiative (LIDC-IDRI)	multi-view convolutional networks (ConvNets)	sensitivities for FP/scan at 1 & 4 are 85.4% and 90.1%
22.	Shradha G Kulkarni and Sahebrao B Bagal	2016	Lung Image Database Consortium and Early Lung Cancer Action Program (LIDC-ELCAP)	Gabor, median and anisotropic diffusion filtering. Watershed algorithm. SVM and KNN classifier	Accuracy of KNN classifier is 95.56% and SVM is 90%

23.	Shubhangi Khobragade et.al	2016	Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC)	Feed forward neural network is used. 7 input neuron of chest radiographs and 3 hidden layer signifies lung diseases as LC	Accuracy obtained is 89.2%
24.	Ruchika Ashima and	2015	Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC)	mean shift algorithm and water shed algorithm	Accuracy 86%
25.	Hao Han, Lihong Liet.al,	2015	Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC)	high-level VQ, rule-based filtering, support vector machine	sensitivity of 82.7% at 4 FPs/scan

2. Materials and Methods

Pre-processing

Figure 2: Process flow diagram of the lung cancer detection method [21].

A. Data Collection : In the first stage input CT images can be obtained from hospitals or publically available dataset such as Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC) and Early Lung Cancer Action Program (ELCAP).

B. Pre-processing: This stage is used to suppress the noise affect and improve the quality of image.

Various filters such as median filter, average filter and adaptive median filter can be used. The median filter removes the noise and retains the sharpness of the image. Accordance to the name, each pixel is replaced by the median value from the neighbourhood pixels. A 3×3 window is used in this filter [21]. In the adaptive median filter, the window size varies with respect to each pixel. Histogram Equalization is used. Image enhancement is the technique which is used to improve the image quality.

- C. Segmentation: Segmentation divides an image into regions. Segmentation is used to locate objects and boundaries. Segmentation is carried out to extract only the part of lungs from the CT scan images. Segmentation should stop when the object has been detected. It consists of applying five methods, namely, k-means, k-median, particle swarm optimization (PSO), inertia-weighted particle swarm optimization (IWPSO), and GCPSO. k-Means Clustering Algorithm: The simplest and conventional method in cluster analysis. This algorithm segregates the given dataset into two or more clusters [22]. PSO is a metaheuristic algorithm used efficiently in medical image analysis [25]. It mimics the social behavior of the birds searching for food [22]. The fundamental idea of PSO is sharing and communicating the information. The GCPSO focuses on a new particle which deals with the current best position in the region. In this task, this particle is treated as a member of the swarm, and the velocity update equation for this new particle is given as follows [20].
- D. Feature extraction: It is an important stage that uses algorithms and techniques to detect and separate various features such as intensity features, texture features and geometric features from the image. There are many techniques used for feature extraction like principle component analysis (PCA), Linear Discriminate Analysis (LDA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), Support Vector Machine (SVM) etc.
- E. Output Image - Nodule detection and Classification: This is the final stage. Based on the features extracted from the image the lung nodule is detected. Classification of nodule can be based on shape, textures and geometric features. Nodule is classified as malignant or benign. The stage of the cancer can be predicted. There are many techniques used for detection and classification such as principle component analysis (PCA), Neural network Classifier (NNC), Linear Discriminate Analysis (LDA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), Chain Code (CC), zoning, Gradient Based Features, Histogram, auto encoders, Deep Neural Networks, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

3. CONCLUSION:

Lung cancer is one of the primary health disorders contributing to the universe's high death rate. In comparison to other malignancies, lung cancer has an extremely poor survival rate. Over decades, only 15% of patients with lung cancer were detected at an early stage, and when it spreads to other organs, the survival rate lowers to 3.5 percent. Early diagnosis of the condition is required to decrease mortality and raise the chances of survival. Because of early detection of the disease, the survival rate has risen from 15% to 49% in recent years. A computed Tomography (CT) picture can detect the presence of lung cancer. CT scans processed with various image processing techniques aid in the early detection of this illness. A substantial amount of effort has been dedicated to developing a CAD system for the identification of lung cancer utilising CT images. It is broken into four stages: nodule detection, pre-processing, segmentation, and classification. This work provides a detailed assessment of several strategies utilised in pre-processing, nodule segmentation, detection, and classification.

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